

Energy efficiency in O-RAN: a closed-loop approach of a cell switch-off use case

Albert Bel¹, Luis Blanco¹, Oriol Font-Bach², Vaishnavi Kasuluru¹,
Ismael Gomez-Miguel², Jordi Baranda¹, Josep Mangués-Bafalluy¹

¹Centre Tecnològic de Telecomunicacions de Catalunya (CTTC/CERCA), Castelldefels, Spain
Emails: {albert.bel, luis.blanco, vaishnavi.kasuluru, jordi.baranda, josep.mangués}@cttc.cat

²SRS, Barcelona, Spain

Emails: {oriol.font, ismael.gomez}@srs.io

Abstract—Energy efficiency in mobile networks has become a key focus of stakeholders in the telecom industry, including vendors, Mobile Network Operators (MNOs), academia, and standardization bodies. Recently, the Third Generation Partnership Project (3GPP) has made notable progress in developing standardized mechanisms to help MNOs achieve substantial energy savings. One of the potential use cases for energy optimization identified by the O-RAN Alliance is the cell switch-off. By adapting the active cell configuration to real-time traffic demands, network resources can be allocated more efficiently. In this demo, we provide a complete setup that, by monitoring and forecasting the PRB loads of the network via an xApp, we enforce a cell switch-off to reduce energy consumption while maintaining the QoS for users.

Index Terms—B5G/6G, Energy efficiency, Open-Source, Open5GS, srsRAN, OSC-RIC

I. INTRODUCTION

Currently, both academia and industry are actively researching new methods for Communications Service Providers (CSPs) to reduce the energy consumption of their network infrastructure. Existing initiatives include those defined by 3GPP in the TS 28.310 standard [1], which focus on deactivating capacity booster cells and User Plane Functions (UPFs) during low-traffic periods. Additionally, the RAN WG3 group is exploring coordination techniques across network interfaces. At the same time, the O-RAN Alliance has outlined energy-saving use cases in its Technical Report on Network Energy Saving Use Cases [2].

Other approaches target improving energy efficiency at the processor and network server level (e.g., through CPU power management and virtualization technologies) and at the site level (e.g., by optimizing cooling systems).

In this context, our demonstration wants to show how energy consumption can be reduced by dynamically adjusting the Radio Access Network (RAN) configuration through predicted traffic loads, thus minimizing resource waste.

As shown in Figure 1, the scenario is based on the existence of two cells, one coverage cell (gNB-DU #1) and one capacity cell (gNB-DU #2). Based on the use case Cell switch-off

presented in [2], the idea we want to showcase is the dynamic switch-off of the capacity cell depending on the predicted traffic load. The use of advanced probabilistic forecasting models, such as LSTM, allows significant gains to be achieved in terms of the reduction in energy consumption. Combining real-time RAN PRB utilization metrics and historical data provides the foundations to implement a decision engine to predict future PRB demands. The decision engine will decide whether the capacity cell can be switched off on the basis of two conditions:

- the forecast of PRB demands are less than a particular threshold
- the total PRB demand is lower than the maximum PRBs that the coverage station can offer

Once the decision is made, the xApp will be responsible for switching off the cell and forcing the UEs to handover from the capacity cell to the coverage cell.

II. SYSTEM ARCHITECTURE

Figure 2 shows the experimental deployment in the EXTREME@xG Test Bed located at CTTC (Castelldefels, Spain). The different components are distributed among three different commercial-off-the-shelf servers. One server runs the RIC (RAN Intelligent Controller) solution, an instance of Open5GS, an instance of Grafana, and influxDB. All the mentioned pieces of software run as docker containers as included in the srsRAN Project [4]¹. Regarding the RAN, we count on two servers connected to a USRP each acting as a radio front-end for over-the-air (OTA) transmission. The B210 model will act as the coverage cell, while the USRP N310 will act as the capacity cell. The last is the front-end that is being monitored, in terms of power and energy consumption, with a TAPO P110 smart plug [7]. The setup is based on two smartphones (UEs) connected to a laptop, which allows remote graphical access and control.

This demonstration aims at showing the capabilities of this O-RAN framework to feature a full deployment of i) Open5GS [3] acting as mobile core, ii) srsRAN Project [4] acting as gNB (based on the CU/DU split and running at

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¹srsRAN Project source code can be found in [5]

Fig. 1. Cell switch-off scenario.

different servers) and iii) O-RAN Alliance Software Community (OSC) [6] framework implementing a near-RT RIC and associated xApps, based on open-source solutions able to reduce energy consumption while maintaining the QoS required by users.

Fig. 2. Architecture scenario.

The demonstration has to separate phases: a first part which consists on the deployment of all necessary components, and a second part where the energy efficiency xApp start monitoring the network and deciding to switch off the capacity cell depending on the AI/ML probabilistic forecasting algorithm.

1) *Deployment phase:* The steps to deploy the complete setup are the following.

- 1) Deployment of the Open5GS Core and the OSC-RIC based on docker deployments at server 1.
- 2) Deployment of the srsRAN CU and DU 1 at server 2.
- 3) Deployment of the srsRAN DU 2 at server 3.
- 4) Switch on two COTS UEs, each one attached to each cell.
- 5) Start xApp for monitoring PRB demands and energy consumption of capacity cell, and
- 6) Deploy a Grafana monitoring system to visualize KPMs and energy reported by the plug.

2) *Energy efficiency xApp operation:* Once the setup is deployed, the xApp will continuously monitor the KPMs

reported by E2 nodes and the energy consumed by the USRP N310. All these measurements are reported and shown in a Grafana dashboard. The xApp will analyze the PRB demands of the E2 nodes, and if it deems that traffic can be served by the coverage cell, it will decide to switch off the capacity cell via an open-source API client [8], thanks to AI/ML probabilistic forecasting algorithm and the conditions explained. Once the capacity cell is switched off, the UE connected to that cell will be enforced to hand over to the coverage cell. Hence, a complete close-loop is achieved at the network.

III. CONCLUSIONS

This demonstration showcases two important things: the deployment of a distributed 5G mobile network, encompassing both Core and RAN functionalities, with a specific focus on deploying O-RAN entities such as near-RT RIC and xApps based on multivendor open source solutions, and, the close-loop achieved by the AI/ML probabilistic forecasting algorithm to facilitate energy efficiency at the network by applying an adaptive monitoring and cell switch off decision based on PRB traffic demands. More concretely, the deployment strategy is to monitor PRB demands of the cells, and based on forecasting algorithms, decide to switch off a capacity cell to reduce energy consumption while maintaining the QoS of users. This pragmatic approach empowers B5G/6G network management, helping it to dynamically adapt and scale according to operational requirements, facilitating decisions driven by closed-loop feedback mechanisms and reducing energy consumption.

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